

Digital Skills

**Difficulty
navigating
complex
websites**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Digital Skills

Difficulty navigating the internet

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Help?

Categories?

Simpler processes?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
operating online in
unstructured
environments such
as social media
platforms and
search engines

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

**Difficulty
understanding
and learning
new processes
without help**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Help?

**A platform for help
and support videos?**

Digital Skills

Need of support in using digital devices

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Digital Skills

Difficulty using
communication
tools such as
messaging and
videocalling apps

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

Difficulty using
keyboards for
example due to
buttons being too
small

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty with online learning

Existing tools

Immersive
Reader

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
understanding
non-standard
symbols or
images used in
place of words

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty avoiding risks online such as viruses, inappropriate content and cyberbullying

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty finding
and paying for
goods and services

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
booking
appointments/
activities
online

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

Lack of computer skills

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

**Difficulty
finding and
accessing
training on web
accessibility**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

**Difficulty
saving specific
information in
an accessible
way**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
accessing digital
devices or tools

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty finding
employment
opportunities
online

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Digital Skills

Difficulty working
from home

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty trusting
new people or
technology

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty finding
non-text options

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

No FAQ section

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty reading
text when there
are no options to
adjust font, size
and colour

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
understanding and
entering captcha
information

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
navigating
complex menus on
apps

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Categories?

Help?

Digital Skills

Lack of awareness
of tools

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Digital Skills

PDFs not
compatible with
T2S tools or
screen readers

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
navigating audio
files to find useful
information

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty creating
online profiles

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulties
creating passwords
and signing in

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Digital Skills

Difficulty
identifying fake
profiles online

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

